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Comparison of bibliographic search strategies for systematic review on kidney and urinary diseases epidemiology for the Global Burden of Disease Study

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Introduction: Systematic review requires conduction of a comprehensive bibliographic search. Comparing different search strategies is essential for choosing those covers all useful data sources.

Methods: Genitourinary Disease Expert Group has performed systematic review of literature for obtaining published data sources for modelling kidney and urinary diseases estimates in the Global Burden of Disease Study. Several search strategies were applied for the literature published and indexed in PubMed and EMBASE between January 1980 and April 2009. Additional unpublished data were obtained by the Institute of Health Metrics and Evaluation.

Results: Initial bibliographic search obtained 29,460 records from PubMed, and 4,247 from EMBASE. After the revision of either abstract or article, 381 and 14 articles were retrieved in full-text for data extraction, respectively (percent of useful articles is 1.3% for PubMed, 0.3% for EMBASE, $\chi^2=28.936$, $P<0.0005$). We applied two search strategies for the PubMed: more sensitive one retrieved 23,352 records, of which 360 (1.5%) were used for data extraction, and provided 7,612 data rows for modelling; more specific strategy retrieved 13,147 records, 325 (2.3%) of which were used for data extraction, and provided 6,507 data rows. More sensitive and more specific PubMed strategies differed in the proportion of full-text sources used for the data extraction ($\chi^2=39.038$, $P<0.0005$), but not in the mean number of rows extracted from article (mean number of rows per one article 20.0 and 21.1, respectively, $P=0.511$).

Conclusions: From all PubMed and EMBASE search strategies we obtained 33,707 records, of which 395 articles were used for extraction of 7,892 data rows for modelling incidence, prevalence, and mortality for kidney and urinary diseases. Application of sensitive search strategy provided more data for modeling, while more specific strategy could be used when resources are limited. Acknowledgements: Boris Bikbov is supported by the EU Horizon2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant No. 703226.